

J.UCS Special Issue on Formal Languages and Automata (WFLA)

Alexandru Mateescu
University of Turku, Turku, Finland
and
Faculty of Mathematics, University of Bucharest,
Bucharest, Romania

This special issue consists of some of the best lectures given at the Workshop on Formal Languages and Automata (WFLA) in Iasi, Romania, September 2 - 3, 1999. This workshop was a satellite event of the conference Fundamentals of Computation Theory (FCT'99) held also in Iasi, Romania, August 30 - September 2, 1999. The workshop was organized by the University A.I. Cuza, Iasi, Romania.

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Alexandru Mateescu